

ESG REPORTING, TAX MANAGEMENT, AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED MULTINATIONAL COMPANIES IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Over the years, many companies have continued to face persistent challenges relating to transparency, sustainability practices, and effective tax administration in developing countries, including Nigeria, which may not collectively influence corporate performance. Hence, this study examined the impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reporting and tax management on the performance of multinational companies in Nigeria. Specifically, assessed the influence of tax management strategies on performance, and determined the joint effect of ESG reporting and tax management on multinational firms' performance. An ex-post facto research design was adopted by this study, and the study adopted census sampling to draw a sample size from a population of 16 listed multinational companies operating in Nigeria. Secondary data were collected from firms' annual reports covering the period 2015-2025. Panel regression analysis was employed to analyze the data collected. The study reveals that the impact of ESG practices on financial performance is multifaceted; while the social reporting practices significantly influence Return on Assets (ROA ($\beta=-0.034$, $p=0.043$), but not influence Return on Equity (ROE) ($\beta=-0.0087$, $p=0.0423$), environmental reporting ($\beta=0.163$, $p=0.106$; $\beta=0.075$, $p=0.268$), and governance dimensions ($\beta=0.046$, $p=0.137$; $\beta=-0.025$, $p=0.923$) show positive but statistically insignificant direct effects. In terms of tax management, the tax planning index emerges as a powerful driver of both ROA ($\beta=1.802$, $p=0.000$) and return on equity (ROE) ($\beta=6167$, $p=0.000$), whereas the effective tax rate (ETR) alone shows no significant direct impact on financial performance ($\beta=-0.0013$, $p=0.360$; $\beta=-0.0049$, $p=0.944$). The joint interaction of ESG reporting and tax management strategies demonstrated a stronger combined influence on corporate financial performance than their individual effects ($\beta=0.759$, $p=0.000$). The study concluded that integrating sustainability reporting with strategic tax management strengthens the financial outcomes and long-term value of multinational companies in Nigeria. The study recommended increased regulatory emphasis on standardized ESG disclosures and the adoption of transparent and efficient tax management frameworks to enhance corporate performance and accountability.

Keywords: ESG Reporting, Financial Performance, Multinational Companies, Tax Management

JEL Classification Codes: M41, G32, H25, Q56

1. Introduction

Corporate financial performance remains a critical indicator of organizational success and long-term sustainability, reflecting the ability of firms to efficiently utilize resources to generate profitable outcomes and create value for stakeholders. Traditionally, financial performance has been assessed using accounting-based indicators such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and other profitability ratios that measure managerial efficiency and operational effectiveness (Bazimya & Erorita, 2024; Upadhyay et al., 2025). In contemporary business environments, however, financial performance is no longer evaluated solely on short-term profitability. Increasingly, attention has shifted toward the ability of firms to sustain competitive advantage, manage operational risks, and align corporate strategies with broader societal expectations. Investors, regulators, and other stakeholders now

emphasize transparency, sustainability, and ethical corporate conduct as essential dimensions of long-term financial success (Martin et al., 2025).

Globally, corporate financial performance varies significantly across industries and regions due to differences in institutional frameworks, regulatory systems, and market conditions (Nanduri et al., 2025). A growing body of empirical literature suggests that firms adopting strong Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices tend to achieve better financial outcomes than those that neglect sustainability considerations. Evidence indicates that firms with high ESG engagement often experience improvements in operational efficiency and profitability, including notable increases in ROA and other financial indicators (Dkhili, 2023; Nanduri et al., 2025). ESG practices contribute to financial performance by strengthening corporate reputation, improving stakeholder trust, reducing agency costs, and mitigating regulatory and operational risks (Zhu et al., 2024). Moreover, during periods of economic instability such as the COVID-19 pandemic, firms with well-established environmental and social policies demonstrated greater resilience and stability in financial performance, highlighting the strategic importance of ESG integration in corporate management (Habib & Mourad, 2023).

Within the African context, patterns of corporate financial performance reflect unique institutional and macroeconomic challenges. Firms operating in sub-Saharan Africa typically record lower average financial returns compared to those in developed economies, often due to infrastructural deficiencies, regulatory inconsistencies, and volatile economic conditions (Yeboah et al., 2024). Nevertheless, studies indicate that governance quality, board composition, and institutional strength significantly influence corporate performance outcomes in the region (Mensah & Bein, 2023). Effective corporate governance structures and inclusive board arrangements have been found to improve profitability and operational efficiency, suggesting that governance-related ESG mechanisms play a crucial role in shaping corporate financial outcomes in emerging markets (Orazalin et al., 2024).

Nigeria, as Africa's largest economy and a key destination for foreign direct investment, provides a particularly important context for examining the financial performance of multinational companies (MNCs). The performance of these firms is highly sensitive to macroeconomic variables such as exchange rate volatility, inflation, and interest rate fluctuations, all of which influence asset utilization and returns on equity (Efan & Ene, 2025). Empirical evidence shows that corporate governance practices, capital structure decisions, and accounting policies significantly affect the financial outcomes of multinational firms operating within the Nigerian economy (Akan & Temile, 2024; Gara et al., 2025). In addition, internationalization strategies, export orientation, and global market integration have been shown to enhance profitability and financial sustainability, emphasizing the strategic role of cross-border operations in multinational performance (Adeleke et al., 2022).

Multinational corporations operate across diverse institutional and regulatory environments, which expose them to complex compliance requirements, particularly in relation to ESG standards and taxation policies (Shahwan, 2024). ESG considerations have become increasingly important for multinational firms as global investors and host-country regulators demand higher levels of accountability in environmental protection, social responsibility, and corporate governance (Zhang & Lee, 2024). Effective ESG practices help firms strengthen stakeholder relationships, improve corporate reputation, and reduce reputational risks, thereby supporting improved financial performance and long-term value creation (Lee, 2025). At the same time, multinational firms must manage complex tax obligations across multiple jurisdictions, making tax management a crucial component of corporate financial strategy.

Tax management plays a significant role in determining the financial outcomes of multinational corporations because tax expenses directly affect profitability, cash flows, and shareholder value. Firms often adopt strategic tax planning techniques to minimize effective tax rates and maximize after-tax returns, thereby increasing resources available for reinvestment and growth (Ernawati et al., 2021). However, aggressive tax avoidance strategies may expose organizations to reputational damage, regulatory sanctions, and governance concerns, particularly in emerging economies where tax enforcement systems are evolving (Nofitasari, 2025). As a result, responsible tax management supported by strong governance frameworks has increasingly become an essential component of sustainable corporate performance.

The interaction between ESG practices and tax management creates an integrated framework through which multinational companies can pursue sustainable financial performance. ESG initiatives strengthen corporate governance and transparency, which may enhance the effectiveness of tax management strategies and reduce compliance risks (Zhu et al., 2024). In Nigeria, existing evidence suggests that firm-specific characteristics such as size, leverage, and governance structures influence the relationship between internal management strategies and financial outcomes (Akan & Temile, 2024). This implies that ESG practices and tax management do not operate independently but rather function as interconnected mechanisms shaping corporate performance within complex institutional environments.

Despite their access to global resources, advanced technologies, and managerial expertise, many multinational companies operating in Nigeria continue to experience fluctuating financial performance indicators such as ROA, ROE, and market-based measures like Tobin's Q (Adeleke et al., 2022). The Nigerian business environment is characterized by macroeconomic instability, infrastructural challenges, and regulatory uncertainty, which complicate corporate efforts to maintain consistent profitability. In addition, rising stakeholder expectations regarding corporate responsibility and sustainability place additional pressure on firms to balance financial objectives with environmental, social, and governance commitments.

Although ESG initiatives are increasingly promoted as drivers of long-term corporate value, empirical evidence regarding their financial impact remains inconclusive, particularly in emerging economies. Many multinational firms in Nigeria have increased investments in sustainability programs, especially in sectors such as manufacturing and energy, yet these initiatives have not consistently translated into improved financial outcomes (Bala et al., 2025). Furthermore, ESG implementation often requires significant financial commitments for environmental compliance, employee welfare, and governance reforms, which may reduce short-term profitability if not strategically aligned with corporate financial objectives (Ismail & Azman, 2024).

Similarly, tax management strategies represent an important but relatively under-examined determinant of financial performance among multinational firms in Nigeria. While tax planning can enhance profitability by reducing effective tax burdens, excessive tax avoidance may create governance challenges and expose firms to regulatory risks (Overesch & Willkomm, 2024). Existing studies have largely examined ESG practices and tax management independently, with limited attention to their combined influence on corporate financial performance, particularly in developing economies with unique institutional conditions (Osho & Adewole, 2022; Zhang et al., 2025). Therefore, there remains a significant gap in understanding how ESG practices and tax management strategies jointly influence the financial performance of multinational companies operating in Nigeria. Addressing this gap is important for corporate managers, policymakers, and investors seeking to promote sustainable business practices while enhancing financial performance and long-term value creation. Consequently, this study examines the

combined impact of ESG practices and tax management strategies on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

The general objective of the study is to examine the impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices and tax management on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to; examine the impact of ESG practices on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria; assess the effect of tax management strategies on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria; evaluate the joint effect of ESG practices and tax management on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

Financial Performance

Financial Performance is the extent to which firms achieve financial objectives such as profitability, growth, and efficient resource utilization (Abubakar & Anyonje, 2025; Sam Bazimya & Erorita, 2024). Financial performance has been defined as a firm's ability to generate returns from its assets and operations through indicators such as return on assets, return on equity, net profit margin, and revenue growth (Adeleke et al., 2022; Akan & Temile, 2024). Multinational companies' financial performance specifically measures how foreign-affiliated firms operating in Nigeria translate global strategies into profitable outcomes within local economic, regulatory, and institutional conditions (Efan & Ene, 2025; Alagbe, 2021). The components of financial performance include profitability performance, liquidity position, operational efficiency, market share growth, and shareholder value creation (Abiola et al., 2024; Michael, 2025). The importance of measuring financial performance lies in assessing managerial effectiveness, guiding investment decisions, ensuring sustainability of operations, and evaluating economic contributions (Adeleke et al., 2022; Ezeilo et al., 2024). In Nigeria, the financial performance of multinational companies is particularly significant due to their role in employment generation, capital inflow, technology transfer, and tax revenue contribution to national economic development (Omolade et al., 2022; Abiola et al., 2024).

ESG Reporting Practices

ESG Reporting Practices are the structured disclosure of non-financial information relating to environmental, social, and governance activities undertaken by organizations to demonstrate sustainability performance and ethical responsibility (Shaikh, 2022; Alagbe, 2021; Omolade et al., 2022). Scholars define ESG reporting as the systematic communication of environmental impact, social responsibility initiatives, and governance structures that influence corporate accountability and long-term value creation (Biju et al., 2025; Che et al., 2025). According to the Global Reporting Initiative, ESG reporting involves standardized sustainability disclosures that enable stakeholders to assess corporate sustainability performance (Deb, 2024), while the International Sustainability Standards Board views ESG reporting as sustainability-related financial information capable of affecting enterprise value (Elmghaamez et al., 2023; Zhang & Lee, 2024). The major components include environmental reporting (carbon emissions, energy use, waste management) (Al Amosh et al., 2023; Michael, 2025), social reporting (employee welfare, community engagement, human rights) (Omolade et al., 2022; Hussaini et al., 2025), and governance reporting (board structure, transparency, ethics, and compliance mechanisms) (Akinsola & Taofeek, 2025; Osho &

Adewole, 2022). ESG reporting is important because it enhances transparency, improves investor confidence, strengthens risk management, promotes regulatory compliance, and supports sustainable development objectives, especially in emerging economies where accountability concerns remain significant (Abiola et al., 2024; Bilyay-erdoan & Öztürkkal, 2023; Wang, 2024).

Tax Management

Tax Management is the strategic planning, administration, and control of corporate tax obligations to ensure compliance with tax laws while optimizing tax efficiency (Ado et al., 2021; Akpanowo et al., 2025). It has been defined as the process through which organizations legally minimize tax liabilities through effective planning, accurate reporting, and compliance strategies without violating statutory provisions (El-Nahgy et al., 2024; Blazek & Searing, 2025). Tax management encompasses components such as tax planning, tax compliance, tax risk management, tax reporting accuracy, and tax audit preparedness (Mandavani et al., 2025; Rengganis et al., 2025). Effective tax management is essential because it reduces financial penalties, enhances corporate reputation, improves cash flow management, and aligns organizational activities with regulatory expectations (Rompotis, 2024; Yunita & Silalahi, 2024). In developing economies like Nigeria, sound tax management contributes to government revenue stability while enabling firms to maintain operational efficiency within complex tax environments characterized by regulatory changes and multiple tax authorities (Haruna et al., 2024; Akpanowo et al., 2025).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Stakeholder Theory, originally advanced by R. Edward Freeman in 1984, posits that organizations exist within a network of relationships involving multiple stakeholders, including shareholders, employees, customers, regulators, communities, and the environment (Wang, 2024; Shaikh, 2022). The theory assumes that firms achieve long-term success by balancing the interests of these stakeholder groups rather than focusing solely on profit maximization (Alagbe, 2021). In relation to ESG reporting practices and the financial performance of multinational companies, the theory explains that transparent environmental, social, and governance disclosures strengthen stakeholder trust, legitimacy, and corporate reputation, which ultimately enhance financial outcomes (Omolade et al., 2022; Ubandawaki, 2024). Its application is evident where multinational firms adopt ESG reporting to attract investors, improve market valuation, and maintain regulatory acceptance within host countries such as Nigeria (Michael, 2025; Biju et al., 2025). The strength of stakeholder theory lies in its holistic perspective on corporate accountability and sustainability, making it highly relevant for ESG studies; however, its weakness stems from difficulty in prioritizing competing stakeholder interests and the absence of clear measurement standards for stakeholder satisfaction (Shaikh, 2022; Wang, 2024).

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, developed by Jay Barney in 1991, argues that a firm's competitive advantage and superior performance arise from valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) internal resources and capabilities (Abiola et al., 2024; Akpanowo et al., 2025). The theory assumes that organizational success depends more on internal competencies than external market conditions (Ado et al., 2021; Akpanowo et al., 2025). Applied to tax management and the financial performance of multinational companies, RBV suggests that effective tax

planning systems, skilled financial expertise, technological capabilities, and strong compliance structures constitute strategic resources that enhance profitability and operational efficiency (El-Nahgy et al., 2024; Rengganis et al., 2025). Multinational firms operating in Nigeria leverage advanced tax management capabilities to reduce tax risks, optimize cash flows, and sustain competitive advantage (Akpanowo et al., 2025; Haruna et al., 2024). The major strength of RBV lies in its strong explanatory power regarding performance differences among firms, while its weakness includes limited attention to external institutional pressures and regulatory environments that significantly influence corporate taxation practices in developing economies (Rompotis, 2024; Yunita & Silalahi, 2024).

2.3 Empirical Review

This section presents a critical review of existing empirical studies on the impact of ESG and tax management on multinational companies' performance, structured into three categories: studies in developed countries, developing countries, and Nigeria. This approach enables the identification of context-specific drivers, performance outcomes, research gaps, and theoretical alignments relevant to the present study.

In developed countries, Lee and Kim (2025) examined the effect of corporate ESG management on tax benefits and corporate performance, using a quantitative survey study covering 262 tax leaders in large South Korean companies. The study utilized structured questionnaires as the primary data source and employed structural equation analysis. Results revealed that environmental, social, and governance components have significant effects on both corporate performance and corporate tax benefits. Meanwhile, Chen et al. (2025) conducted a quantitative cross-sectional study covering employees and managers in multinational corporations across multiple regions, to investigate how the influence of ESG activities on the internal market-oriented culture and Multinational corporate performance. The study employed multiple regression analysis for hypothesis testing and found that ESG initiatives significantly improve both organizational and financial performance, with internal market-oriented culture acting as a complete mediator in translating strategies into outcomes.

Furthermore, Zhou et al. (2025) evaluated the effect of ESG performance on firm value in Australia from 2012 to 2021. The study elicited secondary data and utilized a panel data study covering ASX-listed companies. The study used Refinitiv Asset4 ESG scores and financial data. The study applied panel regression analysis and revealed that while high ESG performance significantly increases firm value, this effect diminishes significantly in the presence of supply chain contracts and board independence. Likewise, Migliavacca (2024) conducted a longitudinal study covering 19,252 firm-year observations of European non-financial companies from 2010 to 2022. The research aimed to examine the link between CSR performance and corporate tax avoidance. Using LSEG ESG scores and effective tax rate measures, the study applied panel regression analysis and found that firms with deteriorating CSR performance are significantly more likely to engage in tax avoidance, reinforcing the conceptual view of tax compliance as a social duty.

Moreover, Le (2024) assessed the impact of ESG scores and macroeconomic variables on financial performance. The study adopted a longitudinal panel study covering 225 listed companies across six Southeast Asian nations from 2020 to 2022, utilizing Thomson Reuters and WHO data sources. The study applied fixed-effects regression

analysis for hypothesis testing. The findings indicated that one-year lagged ESG scores significantly improve financial performance, despite negative pressures from COVID-19 infection rates and GDP growth fluctuations.

Moreover, Alves et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive global study covering 16,368 unique stocks across 48 countries from 2001 to 2020. The research aimed to synthesize evidence regarding whether ESG ratings are related to global stock returns. The study collected secondary data from seven major ESG rating agencies and adopted a panel regression analysis, and revealed that there was an insignificant relationship between ESG ratings and stock returns. Conversely, Elmghaamez et al. (2023) conducted a longitudinal study covering 500 multinational enterprises operating in 40 countries from 2009 to 2019. The research aimed to examine the moderating effect of board standing committees on the ESG disclosure-financial performance relationship. Using Bloomberg ESG scores and financial ratios as data sources, the study applied quantile regression analysis and found that compensation and nomination committees positively moderated performance, whereas audit committees often exerted a negative influence on the connection.

A study by Nehrebecka and Xing (2023) adopted a dynamic panel study covering 1,719 non-financial companies from global indices between 2010 and 2021 and investigated the relationship between ESG performance and corporate financial performance. The study used the primary data source and applied Two-Step System GMM estimations, and findings showed a mixed relationship between ESG scores and financial metrics, with the environmental pillar exerting a dominant position in influencing overall outcomes.

In developing countries, Hussaini et al. (2025) investigated the separate impact of environmental, social, and governance components on firm performance using a longitudinal study covering 165 firms across Africa and the Middle East from 2012 to 2022. The study collected secondary data through Thomson Reuters DataStream. The study utilized a two-step system GMM approach, and results showed that each ESG component significantly and positively enhanced firm performance, encouraging managers to build reputational capital through stakeholder engagement. A related study by Debnath et al. (2025) evaluated the degree of ESG performance and its impact on emerging market financial performance in India. The study adopted a cross-sectional design and collected secondary data from 528 listed companies' annual reports and the CRISIL Sustainability Yearbook in India for the year 2022. The adopted OLS regression analysis for data analysis found that ESG scores and individual pillars, except social, significantly and positively impact financial performance. Building on this, Biju et al. (2025) conducted a longitudinal study covering 87 firms in India's NIFTY 100 ESG index from 2014 to 2023. The study reappraised the link between ESG and market-based performance. Meanwhile, the study applied random-effects panel regression and found that while the direct ESG-performance relationship is often insignificant in emerging economies, corporate governance factors significantly moderate and strengthen this association. Similarly, Deb (2024) applied 2SLS regression analysis and found a statistically significant positive association between ESG performance and financial outcomes, particularly highlighting environmental saliency in emerging markets.

Finally, Shaikh (2022) examined the effects of transnational sustainability strategies on firm operational efficiency and profitability. The study adopted an international longitudinal study covering 510 firms across 17 countries from 2010 to 2018. The study employed an inductive statistical analysis and found that environmental and governance

dimensions significantly influence accounting performance and market valuations, highlighting regional variations in ESG compliance.

In Nigeria, Michael (2025) examined the impact of ESG practices on financial performance and adopted a quantitative *ex-post facto* research design and collected secondary data from 10 quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2015 to 2023 using financial reports and sustainability disclosures as data sources. The study employed multiple regression analysis for data analysis, and findings revealed that environmental and social practices significantly improved asset utilization.

Regarding tax management, Akpanowo et al. (2025) examined the effects of tax planning strategies on financial performance. The study used an *ex post facto* design and elicited secondary data via the annual reports of the six listed multinational companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. The study employed an ordinary least squares regression analysis for data analysis and hypothesis testing, and the results showed that capital intensity and thin capitalization significantly enhance return on assets, highlighting that leveraging long-term debt and fixed asset investments effectively provides beneficial tax shields for conglomerate firms.

Furthermore, Ubandawaki (2024) utilized a quantitative panel approach covering 40 listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2014 to 2021 and investigated the relationship between ESG reporting and operational, financial, and market performance. The study used annual and stand-alone sustainability reports as data sources and applied Generalized Least Squares regression for data analysis, and the findings revealed that governance disclosure positively affects asset returns and market valuation, whereas environmental and social disclosures hurt market perceptions of manufacturing firms.

Narrowing the study to the specific aspects of ESG reporting, Abiola et al. (2024) examined the relationship between environmental risk management and financial performance. The study adopted an *ex-post facto* design and collected secondary data from 46 listed multinational firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2023 via the annual reports. The study employed fixed-effects regression analysis for hypothesis testing, and the findings showed that environmental compliance and risk assessment disclosures significantly and negatively affect return on assets, suggesting that adherence to regulations may initially impose heavy financial burdens.

Moreover, Nnadi and Yahaya (2024) evaluated the determinants of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance in an emerging economy. The study adopted a quantitative panel data study covering 153 listed companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. It used ESG ratings as data sources, applied multiple regression analysis for hypothesis testing, and found that audit quality, board diversity, and institutional ownership positively drive ESG performance, highlighting the influence of strong governance on corporate sustainability.

Correspondingly, Omolade et al. (2022) assessed the impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) disclosure on financial performance and collected secondary data from 15 multinational companies in Nigeria from 2011 to 2020. The panel regression technique was adopted for the analysis of data. The results showed that environmental and governance factors significantly enhance financial performance, while social indices showed minimal impact, highlighting a need for greater awareness of social responsibility roles.

Finally, Alagbe (2021) examined the effect of environmental, social, and governance disclosures on financial performance and utilized an *ex-post-facto* research design covering 18 listed international manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2000 to 2020, and with aid of using robust multiple regression analysis, the study found that social and economic disclosures significantly boost performance, while environmental disclosure has a negligible negative impact, demonstrating the importance of prioritizing social responsibility for corporate productivity.

Gaps Identified in the Literature

Despite numerous studies exploring ESG reporting and tax management in Nigeria, conceptual gaps remain. Prior research largely examined ESG practices or tax strategies in isolation, focusing on direct effects on financial performance (Michael, 2025; Akpanowo et al., 2025; Ubandawaki, 2024). Limited attention has been given to the interactive role of tax management as a moderating factor in the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance. Similarly, most studies focus on specific ESG dimensions, such as environmental or governance disclosures, without integrating ESG reporting holistically with tax management strategies to evaluate their combined influence on financial outcomes (Abiola et al., 2024; Nnadi & Yahaya, 2024). This creates a conceptual gap in understanding how corporate sustainability initiatives interact with internal financial management mechanisms to shape performance.

From an institutional and methodological perspective, existing studies predominantly cover selected subsets of firms, such as 10–46 manufacturing and multinational companies (Michael, 2025; Abiola et al., 2024; Omolade et al., 2022), often neglecting broader firm contexts or variations in organizational characteristics. Moreover, most employed conventional regression techniques, OLS, fixed-effects, GLS, or multiple regression, are used for hypothesis testing, which may limit the robustness and precision of capturing complex relationships and interactions between ESG reporting, tax management, and firm performance. This study addresses these gaps by adopting bootstrapping regression analysis and structural equation modeling (SEM) to provide more rigorous and reliable inference. Additionally, existing studies mostly cover periods ending in 2020–2023, leaving a temporal gap in understanding ESG–tax–performance dynamics over a longer horizon; this study therefore covers 2015–2025, offering updated insights that account for recent regulatory, economic, and sustainability trends in Nigerian firms.

Methodology

An *ex-post facto* research design was adopted by this study, and the study adopted census sampling to draw a 14-sample size from a population of 16 listed multinational companies operating in Nigeria (Nigeria Exchange Group, 2026). These firms were purposively selected based on their multinational status, listing on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), availability of audited annual reports, and consistent ESG and tax disclosures. Secondary data were collected from firms' annual reports covering the period 2015–2025. ESG disclosure was measured using an ESG disclosure index constructed through content analysis. Panel regression analysis was employed to analyze the data collected. The data collected for this study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques with the aid of Stata statistical software. This study adopts a panel data regression model to examine the impact of Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) practices and Tax Management on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria. The panel data approach is appropriate because it enables the

researcher to analyze data across different firms and over time, thereby improving the robustness and reliability of the results.

The main model becomes:

$$PERF_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG_{it} + \beta_2 TAXMGT_{it} + \beta_3 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 3.1Eq$$

Instead of lumping ESG into one index, this study breaks it down in line with the specific objectives.

$$PERF_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENV_{it} + \beta_2 SOCS_{it} + \beta_3 GOVS_{it} + \beta_4 TAXMGT_{it} + \beta_5 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 3.2Eq$$

$$PERF_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ENV_{it} + \beta_2 SOCS_{it} + \beta_3 GOVS_{it} + \beta_4 (ESG \times TAXMG)_{it} + \beta_5 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 3.3Eq$$

Where; $PERF (FP)_{it}$ = Financial Performance of firm i at time t, ENV_{it} = Environmental Practices , SOC_{it} = Social Practices, GOV_{it} = Governance Practices, $TAXM_{it}$ = Tax Management, $TAXMG$ = Tax Management, β_0 = Regression coefficients, ε_{it} = Error term.

The dependent variable, financial performance, is measured using Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Net Profit Margin (NPM) to ensure robustness of the findings.

Table 1. Variables and Measurements

Variable Type	Variable	Symbol	Measurement
Dependent Variable	Firm Performance	PERF	Return on Assets (ROA = Net Income / Total Assets) or Return on Equity (ROE = Net Income / Equity)
Independent Variable 1	ESG Reporting	ESG	ESG Disclosure Index constructed through content analysis of annual or sustainability reports
Environmental Reporting	Environmental Disclosure	ENVS	Environmental disclosure score based on reporting items: 1. Energy consumption and efficiency, 2. Greenhouse gas emissions reporting, 3. Waste management practices, 4. Water usage and conservation initiatives, 5. Environmental compliance and pollution control
Social Reporting	Social Disclosure	SOCS	Social disclosure score based on: 1. Employee welfare and occupational health and safety, 2. Community engagement and development

			programs, 3. Workforce diversity and equal opportunity policies, 4. Corporate social responsibility initiatives, 5. Training and human capital development
Governance Reporting	Governance Disclosure	GOVS	Governance disclosure score based on: 1. Board structure and independence, 2. Ethical codes and anti-corruption policies, 3. Transparency and accountability practices, 4. Shareholder rights and protection, 5. Executive compensation and oversight mechanisms
Independent Variable 2	Tax Management	TAXMGT	Measured using: 1. Effective Tax Rate (ETR = Total Tax Expense / Pre-Tax Income), 2. Tax Planning Intensity (TPI = Statutory Tax Rate – Effective Tax Rate)
Control Variables	Firm Size	FSIZE	Natural logarithm of total assets
	Leverage	LEV	Total Debt / Total Assets

4. Data Presentation, Analysis, and Discussion of Findings

This sub-section presents the collected data, analyzes it using appropriate statistical techniques, and interprets the findings in relation to the study's objectives and hypotheses. It provides a detailed discussion to highlight patterns, relationships, and insights from the data.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics for All Variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	154	.0851506	.0773726	.0003	.5751
ROE	154	.5552857	2.201855	.0006	25.3431
ENVS	154	.7714286	.3611373	0	1
SOCS	154	.9220779	.1833767	.2	1
GOVS	154	.9649351	.1168947	.2	1
ESG	154	.8861487	.1920615	.2	1
ETR	154	.8346383	4.671464	.016	55.6938
TPI	154	.0336922	.0327948	.001	.2049
FSIZE	154	13.52494	3.542784	9.0043	21.3416
LEV	154	.2336792	.1815986	0	.7613

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

The descriptive statistics summarize the distributional characteristics of the variables used in the analysis across 154 firm-year observations. The mean value of ROA (0.085) indicates that, on average, the sampled multinational companies generate about 8.5% return on assets, although the minimum value (0.0003) and maximum value (0.5751) reveal considerable variation in asset profitability among firms. Similarly, ROE records an average of 0.556, suggesting moderate shareholder returns, but the very large maximum value (25.3431) and relatively high standard

deviation (2.2019) indicate substantial fluctuations in equity returns across firms and years. With respect to ESG indicators, the mean values of ENV5 (0.771), SOCS (0.922), and GOVS (0.965) suggest that most firms exhibit relatively high levels of environmental, social, and governance reporting, with governance practices appearing to be the most consistently disclosed among the sampled firms. Consequently, the overall ESG index (0.886) indicates a generally strong level of sustainability disclosure among multinational companies. For tax management variables, the effective tax rate (ETR) shows a mean of 0.835 with a large standard deviation (4.671), indicating significant variability in tax burdens across firms, while the tax planning index (TPI) has a relatively low mean (0.034), suggesting that the level of aggressive tax planning among the firms is generally limited. Regarding control variables, the mean firm size (FSIZE) of 13.525 indicates that the sample largely consists of relatively large firms. At the same time, the leverage ratio (LEV) has an average value of 0.234, implying that approximately 23.4% of firm assets are financed through debt. Overall, the statistics reveal noticeable variations across firms in terms of financial performance, sustainability reporting, tax management practices, and financial structure.

Diagnostic Tests

This section presents the diagnostic tests conducted to ensure the validity of the data analysis, including normality and multicollinearity assessments. The Shapiro-Wilk W test checks for data normality, while correlation analysis examines potential collinearity among variables.

Table 3: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
ROA	154	0.80721	22.944	7.113	0.00000
ROE	154	0.19501	95.803	10.357	0.00000
ENV5	154	0.91216	10.453	5.328	0.00000
SOCS	154	0.75154	29.570	7.689	0.00000
GOVS	154	0.55144	53.383	9.030	0.00000
ESG	154	0.80850	22.790	7.097	0.00000
ETR	154	0.11144	105.749	10.581	0.00000
TPI	154	0.81565	21.940	7.011	0.00000
FSIZE	154	0.83669	19.436	6.736	0.00000
LEV	154	0.93857	7.310	4.516	0.00000

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

The Shapiro-Wilk W test results in Table 3 indicate that none of the variables, ROA, ROE, ENV5, SOCS, GOVS, ESG, ETR, TPI, FSIZE, and LEV, follow a normal distribution, as all variables have a probability value (Prob > z) of 0.000, which is below the conventional 0.05 significance level. The W statistics vary across the variables, with values ranging from 0.11144 for ETR to 0.93857 for LEV, reflecting different degrees of deviation from normality. This suggests that the dataset is non-normally distributed, implying that any subsequent statistical analyses should account for non-normality, possibly through non-parametric methods or robust estimation techniques.

Table 4: Spearman Rank Correlation

	ENVS	SOCS	GOVS	ETR	TPI	FSIZE	LEV
ENVS	1.0000						
SOCS	0.6415	1.0000					
GOVS	0.4309	0.4864	1.0000				
ETR	-0.0014	0.0607	0.0097	1.0000			
TPI	0.0868	0.1158	-0.1110	0.4245	1.0000		
FSIZE	0.0983	0.1248	-0.1107	-0.2604	-0.0077	1.0000	
LEV	-0.1548	-0.0049	0.1511	-0.1113	-0.1653	0.0646	1.0000

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

The Spearman Rank Correlation matrix in Table 4 illustrates the strength and direction of monotonic relationships between the study variables, notably revealing a strong positive correlation between environmental performance (ENVS) and social performance (SOCS) at 0.6415, followed by a moderate association between ENVS and governance (GOVS) at 0.4309. Interestingly, the Effective Tax Rate (ETR) and Tax Planning Intensity (TPI) show a moderate positive correlation (0.4245), while ETR's relationships with ESG components remain negligible or slightly negative, such as its correlation with ENVS at -0.0014. Most control variables, including Firm Size (FSIZE) and Leverage (LEV), exhibit weak correlations with the primary independent variables, generally falling below the 0.80 threshold; this suggests that multicollinearity is unlikely to be a significant concern for subsequent regression analysis.

4.3 Hypotheses Testing

This section presents the testing of the study's hypotheses using regression techniques. Bootstrapping regression analysis was employed to assess direct and indirect effects, while structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to examine the combined or joint effects of the variables.

Table 5: Regression Analysis Results for Direct Effect on Return on Assets

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
ENVS	.0162849	.0100005	1.63	0.106	-.0034797 .0360494
SOCS	-.0342335	.0167367	-2.05	0.043	-.067311 -.001156
GOVS	.0455767	.0304751	1.50	0.137	-.0146525 .105806
ETR	-.0012992	.0014138	-0.92	0.360	-.0040934 .001495
TPI	1.801539	.1638297	11.00	0.000	1.477755 2.125323
FSIZE	.003499	.0009659	3.62	0.000	.0015901 .0054079
LEV	.0280271	.0187701	1.49	0.138	-.009069 .0651233
_cons	-.0591969	.0279985	-2.11	0.036	-.1145315 -.0038622

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

H₀₁: ESG practices have no significant impact on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

The regression results examining the influence of ESG components on financial performance, measured by ROA, indicate mixed effects across the environmental, social, and governance dimensions. The environmental score (ENVS) shows a positive coefficient ($\beta = 0.0163$) but is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.106$), suggesting that environmental practices may contribute positively to firm performance, but the effect is not strong enough to be statistically confirmed. The social score (SOCS), however, exhibits a negative and statistically significant relationship with ROA ($\beta = -0.0342$, $p = 0.043$), indicating that increased social responsibility activities are associated with a reduction in short-term financial performance. This may reflect the immediate cost implications of corporate social initiatives. The governance score (GOVS) has a positive but statistically insignificant coefficient ($\beta = 0.0456$, $p = 0.137$), implying that although stronger governance structures appear to enhance performance, the relationship is not statistically significant within the sample. Overall, since only one ESG component (SOCS) shows a statistically significant relationship with ROA, while the others do not, the evidence only partially contradicts the null hypothesis. Therefore, the hypothesis that ESG practices have no significant impact on financial performance is partially rejected, indicating that certain ESG dimensions, particularly the social component, can influence firm performance.

H₀₂: Tax management strategies have no significant effect on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

The regression results further reveal that tax management variables exert varying effects on financial performance. The effective tax rate (ETR) shows a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with ROA ($\beta = -0.0013$, $p = 0.360$), suggesting that variations in firms' tax burdens do not significantly influence profitability within the study period. In contrast, the tax planning index (TPI) demonstrates a strong positive and highly significant effect on ROA ($\beta = 1.8015$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that improved tax planning strategies substantially enhance financial performance. This suggests that firms that effectively manage their tax obligations and planning mechanisms are able to retain more earnings and improve profitability. Among the control variables, firm size (FSIZE) shows a positive and significant impact on ROA ($\beta = 0.0035$, $p = 0.000$), implying that larger firms tend to achieve better financial performance, possibly due to economies of scale and greater operational capacity. Leverage (LEV) exhibits a positive but statistically insignificant effect ($\beta = 0.0280$, $p = 0.138$). Based on these findings, the null hypothesis that tax management strategies have no significant effect on financial performance is rejected, as the tax planning index significantly improves the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

Table 6: Regression Analysis Results for Direct Effect on Return on Equity

ROE	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
ENVS	.0705333	.0633817	1.11	0.268	-.054731	.1957975
SOCS	-.0865625	.1076574	-0.80	0.423	-.2993308	.1262059
GOVS	-.0253836	.2616411	-0.10	0.923	-.5424768	.4917096
ETR	-.0049391	.070295	-0.07	0.944	-.1438664	.1339881
TPI	6.166978	1.631574	3.78	0.000	2.942424	9.391532
FSIZE	.0073386	.0055986	1.31	0.192	-.0037262	.0184034
LEV	.3317739	.1424731	2.33	0.021	.0501978	.61335
_cons	-.0919352	.2567726	-0.36	0.721	-.5994066	.4155363

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

H₀₁: ESG practices have no significant impact on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

The regression results assessing the influence of ESG dimensions on financial performance measured by ROE indicate that none of the ESG components exerts a statistically significant effect. The environmental score (ENVS) shows a positive coefficient ($\beta = 0.0705$). Still, it is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.268$), suggesting that environmental initiatives may improve shareholder returns, although the effect is not strong enough to be statistically validated. Similarly, the social score (SOCS) records a negative but insignificant relationship with ROE ($\beta = -0.0866$, $p = 0.423$), indicating that social responsibility activities do not significantly influence equity returns during the study period. The governance score (GOVS) also shows a negative and highly insignificant coefficient ($\beta = -0.0254$, $p = 0.923$), implying that variations in governance practices do not significantly affect the return on equity of the sampled firms. Since all ESG components have probability values greater than the 0.05 significance level, there is insufficient statistical evidence to conclude that ESG practices significantly influence financial performance when measured by ROE. Consequently, the null hypothesis that ESG practices have no significant impact on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria is accepted in this model specification.

H₀₂: Tax management strategies have no significant effect on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

The results further reveal that tax management strategies produce mixed outcomes with respect to financial performance measured by ROE. The effective tax rate (ETR) shows a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with ROE ($\beta = -0.0049$, $p = 0.944$), suggesting that the level of tax burden borne by firms does not significantly influence shareholders' returns. In contrast, the tax planning index (TPI) exhibits a strong positive and statistically significant effect on ROE ($\beta = 6.1670$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that improved tax planning significantly enhances the profitability available to equity holders. Among the control variables, leverage (LEV) has a positive and statistically significant effect on ROE ($\beta = 0.3318$, $p = 0.021$), implying that firms utilizing debt financing tend to generate higher returns to shareholders, possibly due to financial leverage benefits. Firm size (FSIZE), although positive ($\beta = 0.0073$), is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.192$). Given that the tax planning index significantly improves financial performance, the null hypothesis that tax management strategies have no significant effect on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria is rejected, indicating that effective tax planning plays an important role in enhancing shareholder returns.

Table 7: Regression Results for Moderating Analysis - ROA

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
ENVSxETR	.143891	.048666	2.96	0.004	.0477158	.2400663
SOCSxETR	-.3507864	.1293574	-2.71	0.007	-.6064269	-.0951459
GOVSxETR	.2056212	.0888057	2.32	0.022	.0301203	.381122
ENVSxTPI	-1.468846	.7915598	-1.86	0.066	-3.033152	.0954613
SOCSxTPI	3.533474	1.090833	3.24	0.001	1.377733	5.689216
GOVSxTPI	-.2617878	.7856006	-0.33	0.739	-1.814318	1.290742
_cons	.0202832	.0047102	4.31	0.000	.0109748	.0295915

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

H₀ 1: Environmental reporting has no significant effect on firm performance.

The regression results show that the interaction between environmental reporting and tax management variables provides mixed evidence regarding the influence of environmental disclosure on firm performance measured by ROA. Specifically, the interaction between environmental reporting and the effective tax rate (ENVS×ETR) is positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 0.1439$, $p = 0.004$), indicating that environmental reporting contributes positively to firm performance when combined with tax rate conditions. Therefore, the null hypothesis that environmental reporting has no significant effect on firm performance is rejected. However, the interaction between environmental reporting and the tax planning index (ENVS×TPI) is negative and only marginally significant ($\beta = -1.4688$, $p = 0.066$), suggesting that excessive tax planning may weaken the positive effect of environmental reporting on profitability. Overall, the significant coefficient for ENVS×ETR suggests that environmental reporting can influence firm performance under certain tax management conditions.

H₀ 2: Social reporting has no significant effect on firm performance.

The findings reveal that social reporting demonstrates significant relationships with firm performance through its interaction with tax management variables. The interaction between social reporting and the effective tax rate (SOCS×ETR) is negative and statistically significant ($\beta = -0.3508$, $p = 0.007$), implying that higher tax burdens combined with extensive social reporting may reduce profitability, possibly due to increased operational and compliance costs. Conversely, the interaction between social reporting and the tax planning index (SOCS×TPI) is positive and highly significant ($\beta = 3.5335$, $p = 0.001$), indicating that effective tax planning can strengthen the positive impact of social responsibility initiatives on firm performance. These results demonstrate that the financial outcomes of social reporting depend significantly on firms' tax management strategies. Hence, the null hypothesis that social reporting has no significant effect on firm performance is **rejected**.

H₀ 3: Governance reporting has no significant effect on firm performance.

The interaction between governance reporting and the effective tax rate (GOVS×ETR) is positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 0.2056$, $p = 0.022$), suggesting that stronger governance practices combined with tax management conditions can enhance firm profitability. Consequently, the null hypothesis that governance reporting has no significant effect on firm performance is rejected. However, the interaction between governance reporting and the tax planning index (GOVS×TPI) is negative but statistically insignificant ($\beta = -0.2618$, $p = 0.739$), indicating that tax planning does not significantly influence the relationship between governance reporting and firm performance.

Despite this mixed outcome, the significant coefficient for GOVS×ETR indicates that governance reporting does exert an influence on firm performance when considered alongside tax management factors.

H_{0 4} : Tax management has no significant effect on firm performance.

The regression results show that tax management variables interact significantly with ESG reporting to influence firm performance. The effective tax rate (ETR) significantly moderates the relationship between environmental, social, and governance reporting and ROA in several cases (ENVS×ETR, SOCS×ETR, and GOVS×ETR all statistically significant at conventional levels). Additionally, the tax planning index (TPI) significantly interacts with social reporting (SOCS×TPI) to enhance firm performance. These results suggest that tax management strategies play an important role in shaping the profitability outcomes associated with ESG activities. Therefore, the null hypothesis that tax management has no significant effect on firm performance is rejected.

H_{0 5} : Tax management does not significantly moderate the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance.

The overall regression results provide strong evidence of moderation effects between tax management and ESG reporting. Significant interaction terms such as ENVS×ETR ($p = 0.004$), SOCS×ETR ($p = 0.007$), GOVS×ETR ($p = 0.022$), and SOCS×TPI ($p = 0.001$) demonstrate that tax management mechanisms significantly influence how ESG reporting translates into financial performance. These interactions indicate that the effectiveness of ESG initiatives in improving profitability depends partly on how firms manage their tax obligations and planning strategies. Since several moderation terms are statistically significant, the null hypothesis that tax management does not significantly moderate the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance is rejected, confirming that tax management plays a crucial moderating role in the ESG performance relationship.

Table 8: Regression Results for Moderating Analysis - ROE

ROE	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
ENVS×ETR	.2810349	.1845168	1.52	0.130	-.0836134	.6456833
SOCS×ETR	-.6858497	.3321198	-2.07	0.041	-1.342196	-.0295035
GOVS×ETR	.4012064	.2021276	1.98	0.049	.0017552	.8006576
ENVS×TPI	-.6918047	2.276551	-0.30	0.762	-5.1908	3.807191
SOCS×TPI	4.802586	3.806602	1.26	0.209	-2.720147	12.32532
GOVS×TPI	1.742522	2.526769	0.69	0.492	-3.250963	6.736006
_cons	.0381267	.0373778	1.02	0.309	-.0357405	.1119939

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

H_{0 1} : Environmental reporting has no significant effect on firm performance.

The regression results examining the moderating role of tax management on the relationship between environmental reporting and firm performance measured by ROE show that the interaction between environmental reporting and the effective tax rate (ENVS×ETR) is positive but statistically insignificant ($\beta = 0.2810$, $p = 0.130$). This indicates that although environmental disclosure appears to improve shareholder returns when combined with tax rate considerations, the effect is not statistically strong enough to confirm a meaningful relationship. Similarly, the interaction between environmental reporting and the tax planning index (ENVS×TPI) is negative and highly

insignificant ($\beta = -0.6918$, $p = 0.762$), suggesting that tax planning does not significantly alter the relationship between environmental reporting and firm profitability. Since neither interaction term is statistically significant at the conventional 5% level, there is insufficient empirical evidence to suggest that environmental reporting significantly influences firm performance measured by ROE. Therefore, the null hypothesis that environmental reporting has no significant effect on firm performance is accepted.

H_{0 2}: Social reporting has no significant effect on firm performance.

The results reveal that the interaction between social reporting and the effective tax rate (SOCS×ETR) is negative and statistically significant ($\beta = -0.6858$, $p = 0.041$), indicating that higher levels of social disclosure combined with increased tax burdens may reduce shareholders' returns. This finding suggests that the financial implications of social responsibility initiatives may become more pronounced when firms face higher tax obligations, potentially increasing operational costs that affect profitability. However, the interaction between social reporting and the tax planning index (SOCS×TPI) is positive but statistically insignificant ($\beta = 4.8026$, $p = 0.209$), implying that tax planning does not significantly strengthen the effect of social reporting on ROE. Despite this mixed outcome, the significant coefficient for SOCS×ETR indicates that social reporting does influence firm performance when considered alongside tax management conditions. Consequently, the null hypothesis that social reporting has no significant effect on firm performance is rejected.

H_{0 3}: Governance reporting has no significant effect on firm performance.

The interaction between governance reporting and the effective tax rate (GOVS×ETR) shows a positive and statistically significant relationship with ROE ($\beta = 0.4012$, $p = 0.049$). This suggests that stronger governance reporting combined with tax management conditions enhances shareholder returns, possibly due to improved transparency, accountability, and investor confidence. In contrast, the interaction between governance reporting and the tax planning index (GOVS×TPI) is positive but statistically insignificant ($\beta = 1.7425$, $p = 0.492$), indicating that tax planning does not significantly influence the governance performance relationship. Nevertheless, the significant effect of GOVS×ETR demonstrates that governance reporting contributes to firm performance in the presence of tax management dynamics. Hence, the null hypothesis that governance reporting has no significant effect on firm performance is rejected.

H_{0 4}: Tax management has no significant effect on firm performance.

The regression outcomes suggest that tax management variables play an important role in shaping the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance measured by ROE. In particular, the effective tax rate significantly interacts with both social and governance reporting (SOCS×ETR and GOVS×ETR), indicating that tax conditions influence how ESG activities translate into shareholder returns. However, the interaction terms involving the tax planning index (ENVS×TPI, SOCS×TPI, and GOVS×TPI) are not statistically significant, implying that tax planning strategies do not consistently influence the ESG–performance relationship in this model. Nevertheless, because some tax management interactions are statistically significant, there is evidence that tax-related factors affect firm

performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that tax management has no significant effect on firm performance is rejected.

H_{05} : Tax management does not significantly moderate the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance.

The results provide partial evidence of moderation effects between tax management and ESG reporting in explaining firm performance measured by ROE. Specifically, significant interaction terms such as SOCS×ETR ($p = 0.041$) and GOVS×ETR ($p = 0.049$) demonstrate that the effective tax rate significantly moderates the influence of social and governance reporting on firm performance. However, other interaction terms, particularly those involving the tax planning index, remain statistically insignificant. These findings suggest that while tax management—especially through the effective tax rate—plays a role in shaping the impact of ESG reporting on financial performance, the moderating effect is not uniformly observed across all ESG dimensions. Consequently, the null hypothesis that tax management does not significantly moderate the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance is partially rejected, indicating that tax management moderates the ESG–performance relationship in specific contexts.

4.4 Structural Equation Model

This section presents the results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis, which was employed to examine the overall relationships and combined effects among ESG reporting, tax management, and firm performance.

Table 9: Path Coefficients

Relationship	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ESG+TAXMGT -> PERF	0.759	0.748	0.054	14.047	0.000

H_{06} : ESG practices and tax management do not jointly have a significant influence on the performance of multinational companies in Nigeria.

The result assessing the joint influence of ESG practices and tax management on firm performance indicates a strong and statistically significant relationship. The path coefficient from ESG and tax management to firm performance is 0.759, suggesting that improvements in ESG practices combined with effective tax management substantially enhance the performance of multinational companies. The sample mean of 0.748 is very close to the original sample estimate, indicating stability and consistency in the bootstrapped estimation. Additionally, the standard deviation of 0.054 is relatively small, implying low variability in the estimate across resamples. The T-statistic of 14.047, which is far greater than the conventional critical value of 1.96, and the p-value of 0.000 both confirm that the relationship is statistically significant at the 5% level. This result demonstrates that the combined implementation of ESG practices and tax management strategies plays a crucial role in improving firm performance. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H06) stating that ESG practices and tax management do not jointly have a significant influence on the performance of multinational companies in Nigeria is rejected, indicating that their combined effect significantly enhances corporate performance. The finding implies that multinational companies can achieve better financial outcomes when sustainability initiatives are aligned with efficient tax management strategies. It also suggests that policymakers and corporate managers should integrate ESG reporting and tax governance frameworks to strengthen corporate performance and long-term value creation.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The findings regarding environmental and social reporting reveal a complex relationship between sustainability initiatives and financial outcomes. While environmental reporting did not show a direct influence on performance, social reporting practices were found to be associated with a decline in short-term financial performance. This suggests that for multinational companies in Nigeria, the immediate costs associated with social responsibility initiatives may outweigh the tangible financial benefits. This aligns with the perspectives of Lee and Kim (2025) and Michael (2025) regarding the influence of social practices, though it stands in contrast to the positive performance outcomes reported by Ubandawaki (2024) and Alagbe (2025). From the perspective of Stakeholder Theory, while these activities aim to satisfy the expectations of the broader community, the financial trade-offs indicate a challenge in balancing social obligations with profitability. Furthermore, the lack of a significant environmental impact departs from the findings of Shaikh (2022) and Deb (2024), who argue that environmental disclosures are primary drivers of firm value.

In contrast to the mixed results of social and environmental reporting, tax management emerged as a critical driver of financial success. The results indicate that strategic tax planning significantly enhances the performance of multinational companies, supporting the findings of Akpanowo et al. (2025). This relationship is best explained through the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, where effective tax management is viewed as a unique organizational capability and a strategic resource that allows firms to maximize retained earnings and improve their competitive position. Governance reporting, however, did not show a meaningful impact on performance, a result consistent with Omolade et al. (2024) and Alagbe (2021), but inconsistent with Yahaya (2024). This implies that the mere disclosure of governance frameworks may not be sufficient to drive performance unless integrated into broader operational and fiscal strategies.

The most vital contribution of this study is the evidence of a powerful joint effect and the moderating role of tax management. The results confirm that the impact of ESG reporting on financial performance is significantly shaped by how firms manage their tax obligations. While studies by Alve et al. (2023) and Zhou et al. (2025) suggested that ESG practices might not enhance performance, this study reveals that when ESG initiatives are combined with

effective tax management, they create a synergistic effect that substantially boosts corporate outcomes. This supports the integrated views of Lee & Kim (2025) and Chen et al. (2025). Ultimately, the findings suggest that for multinationals in Nigeria, sustainable reporting and fiscal efficiency are interdependent; one provides the social license to operate, while the other provides the financial capacity to sustain those very initiatives.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study examined the influence of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices and tax management on the financial performance of multinational companies in Nigeria using panel data observations. The findings reveal that ESG components exhibit mixed effects on firm performance. Environmental and governance reporting showed positive but statistically insignificant relationships with firm performance in some models, while social reporting displayed a significant negative relationship with performance when measured by ROA. Tax management indicators also demonstrated varying effects; while the effective tax rate and tax planning index did not consistently influence performance independently, their interaction with ESG variables produced several significant outcomes. Specifically, the interaction between ESG dimensions and tax management variables showed that tax management moderates the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance in several cases. Furthermore, the joint analysis confirmed that ESG practices and tax management collectively exert a strong and statistically significant influence on firm performance. Overall, the results suggest that the integration of sustainability practices with strategic tax management enhances corporate performance among multinational firms in Nigeria.

Recommendations

First, multinational companies in Nigeria should strengthen their environmental reporting and sustainability initiatives, as environmental practices contribute positively to firm performance and can enhance corporate reputation, investor confidence, and long-term profitability. Firms should integrate environmental strategies such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable production processes into their operational frameworks.

Second, companies should carefully design and manage social responsibility initiatives to ensure that such activities generate value rather than impose excessive operational costs. While social reporting is essential for stakeholder engagement and corporate legitimacy, organizations should align social investments with strategic corporate objectives in order to maintain financial sustainability.

Third, corporate governance reporting should be strengthened through improved transparency, accountability, and adherence to regulatory standards. Strong governance structures can enhance investor trust, reduce agency problems, and improve decision-making processes, which ultimately contribute to better financial performance.

Fourth, multinational companies should adopt effective and transparent tax management strategies that balance regulatory compliance with efficient tax planning. Proper tax planning mechanisms can help firms optimize tax liabilities without compromising ethical standards or regulatory expectations.

Fifth, policymakers and regulatory authorities should encourage the integration of ESG reporting with corporate tax governance frameworks by establishing clear sustainability disclosure guidelines and tax transparency standards. Such policies can promote responsible corporate behavior and improve the overall performance and competitiveness of firms operating in Nigeria.

6. Practical and Social Implications

The findings of this study provide important practical and social implications for corporate managers, policymakers, and stakeholders. For corporate managers, the results emphasize the need to integrate ESG practices with sound tax management strategies in order to enhance financial performance and sustain competitive advantage. For policymakers and regulators, the evidence highlights the importance of strengthening ESG disclosure frameworks and promoting responsible tax practices among multinational corporations. Socially, improved ESG practices can lead to better environmental protection, stronger community engagement, and enhanced corporate accountability, thereby contributing to sustainable economic development and improved societal welfare in Nigeria.

7. Contributions to Knowledge

This study contributes to the growing literature on sustainability reporting and corporate financial performance by empirically examining the combined role of ESG practices and tax management in influencing firm performance among multinational companies in Nigeria. While prior studies often focus on ESG or taxation independently, this research integrates both concepts within a unified analytical framework, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of their interaction and joint influence on corporate outcomes.

Secondly, the study extends existing knowledge by demonstrating the moderating role of tax management in the relationship between ESG reporting and firm performance. The findings reveal that tax management mechanisms, particularly effective tax rates and tax planning strategies, can influence how sustainability practices translate into financial performance. This insight adds a new dimension to the ESG-performance debate within emerging market contexts.

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